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Imprinting system alterations in humans with multiple sclerosis.

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We studied total transcription in the peripheral blood and gray matter of humans with multiple sclerosis. We describe here significant changes in expression of plant homeodomain epigenetic effectors including *Phf19*, *Phf20* and *Phf21b* in the CNS of humans with an neurologic autoimmune disease.